

NOTES

Azo Complexes : Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts with *o*-Carboxylbenzeneazo-2-Naphthol

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A number of stable adducts of alkali metal salts with *o*-carboxylbenzeneazo-2-naphthol of the general formula ML.COOHBAN (ML=Li, Na or K salt ; COOHBAN=*o*-carboxylbenzeneazo-2-naphthol) have been synthesised. Analytical data showed that one molecule of the alkali metal salt combined with one molecule of COOHBAN. Based on infrared data, possible mode of coordination of COOHBAN in adducts has been suggested.

Experimental

The ligand COOHBAN (m.p. 274°) was prepared by standard method¹. Solutions of the alkali metal salts used were prepared in 95% ethanol.

General method of preparation of the adducts :

To a hot absolute ethanol solution of COOHBAN, alkali metal salts (ethanolic solution) were added in 2 : 1 molar ratio. The mixture was refluxed over hot plate using magnetic stirrer for ~0.5 hr. The solution on keeping yielded crystalline solid adducts. The crystals were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried in an oven at 80°.

Results and Discussion

The adducts are stable when stored under dry condition in a desiccator, but decompose in the pre-

TABLE I

Compound	Colour	Melting/decom. temp. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			
			C	H	N	M
COOHBAN=L'	Red	274 m	70.00 (69.99)	4.14 (4.11)	9.58 (9.60)	—
Li1N2N.L'	Deep red	325 d	68.99 (68.79)	3.62 (3.82)	9.21 (8.91)	— (1.48)
Na1N2N.L'	Deep red	320 d	66.52 (66.53)	3.71 (3.69)	8.65 (8.62)	4.69 (4.72)
K1N2N.L'	Deep red	316 d	64.55 (64.41)	3.54 (3.58)	8.48 (8.35)	7.52 (7.75)
Na8HQ.L'	Deep red	321 d	70.86 (70.59)	3.84 (3.92)	9.52 (9.37)	4.82 (5.01)
K8HQ.L'	Deep red	315 d	68.42 (61.21)	3.65 (3.79)	8.94 (8.84)	7.98 (8.21)
NaONP.L'	Deep red	323 d	61.11 (60.93)	3.32 (3.58)	9.34 (9.27)	4.92 (5.07)
KONP.L'	Deep red	320 d	59.12 (58.84)	3.29 (3.41)	9.14 (8.95)	8.12 (8.31)
Na2H3NA.L'	Deep red	323 d	66.99 (66.93)	3.54 (3.78)	5.84 (5.57)	4.32 (4.58)
K2H3NA.L'	Deep red	317 d	65.11 (64.86)	3.45 (3.66)	4.84 (5.40)	7.38 (7.52)
NaSa1H.L'	Deep red	315 d	66.89 (66.55)	3.65 (3.89)	6.56 (6.42)	5.12 (5.27)
NaSa1A.L'	Deep red	324 d	61.79 (61.50)	3.53 (3.76)	6.34 (6.19)	4.89 (5.08)
Na.anth.L'	Deep red	322 d	64.12 (63.85)	3.64 (3.99)	9.82 (9.31)	4.89 (5.09)
K.anth.L'	Deep red	314 d	61.97 (61.67)	3.62 (3.85)	9.01 (8.99)	8.11 (8.35)
Na.acac.L'	Deep red	318 d	63.99 (63.76)	4.32 (4.59)	6.94 (6.76)	5.13 (5.55)
K.acac.L'	Deep red	312 d	61.59 (61.39)	4.12 (4.42)	6.95 (6.51)	8.89 (9.06)

COOHBAN=*o*-carboxylbenzeneazo-2-naphthol, 1N2N=1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8HQ=8-hydroxyquinoline, ONP=*o*-nitrophenol, 2H3NA=2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, Sa1H=salicylaldehyde, Sa1A=salicylic acid, anth=anthranilic acid, acac=acetyl acetone.

sence of moisture. The azo compounds of COOHBAN are all deep red coloured and are thermally stable. When heated, they decompose at a temperature much higher than the melting point of the ligand and also of the alkali metal salts. The colour, melting or decomposition temperatures and analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

The presence of COOH and OH groups in the *o*- and *o'*-position to the azo group suggested the possibility of strong intra-molecular hydrogen bonding in ligand COOHBAN.

The -OH stretching frequency at 3050 cm⁻¹ (br) of the ligand is missing in the adducts. However, in KSCN adduct, the band appears at higher frequency (3450 cm⁻¹). Broad band with two sub-maxima at 2600 and 2450 cm⁻¹ are obtained in the adducts, whereas the ligand only shows one band at 2450 cm⁻¹ with lower intensity due to stronger hydrogen bonding.

The asymmetric stretch of the C=O group shows up at 1710 cm⁻¹ in the ligand. In the alkali metal adducts, it appears between 1620-1630 cm⁻¹, and is suggestive² of coordination of C=O group to the alkali metals.

The -N=N- frequency in the ligand shows up at 1580 cm⁻¹. In the alkali metal adducts, this appears between 1560-1570 cm⁻¹.

From the infrared spectra of the ligand and adducts, it may be suggested that the attachment is through -OH, C=O, and -N=N- groups of the ligand COOHBAN.

References

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Zn(II) and Cd(II) with Iminodiacetic Acid as Primary Ligand and Amino Acids as Secondary Ligand

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BHATTACHARYA and co-workers have investigated^{1,2} the mixed ligand system (MAL) involving bivalent metal ions like Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺ and histidine, iminodiacetic acid or nitrilotriacetic acid as primary ligand and polyhydroxy phenols or amino acids as secondary ligand. Various mixed ligand complexes with iminodiacetic acid (IMDA)³ as the primary ligand have been studied. In the present investigation, attempts have been made to study the formation constants of the title systems in

presence of equivalent and excess amount of secondary ligand L, using modified form of Irving-Rossotti⁴ titration technique.

IMDA is known to form 1:1 complex with Zn(II) or Cd(II) at pH ~6 and ~6.5, respectively and the complex is stable at higher pH, where the combination of secondary ligand starts. The reaction can be shown as follows:

$$K_{MAL}^{MA} = \frac{[MAL]}{[MA][L]}$$

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. quality. Zn(II) and Cd(II) perchlorates were prepared from their respective carbonates and the metal content were determined and checked. Conductivity water was used in the preparation of all the solutions.

The experimental set up and methods of calculations described by Bhattacharya and co-workers¹ were employed. The measurements were carried out at 30°.

The nature of the potentiometric titration curves was interpreted by the method adopted in earlier publications. In the secondary ligand two equivalent extra acid was added to account for the extra hydrogen ions liberated due to the combination of primary ligand, IMDA. \bar{n} and pL were calculated using the same equation as in earlier cases⁵. Precise values of K_{MAL}^{MA} were obtained by using the method of averages⁶. The values are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The order of the formation constants of the ternary complexes is the same as that for the binary complexes^{7,8}. However, the values of K_{MAL}^{MA} are significantly lower than the values of the first formation constant K_{ML}^M of the binary complexes and are slightly lower than the second formation constant $K_{ML_2}^M$ of the binary complexes. The same order is observed in the case of excess amount of the secondary ligand L.

The results can be explained by considering that the electrostatic repulsion between the primary ligand iminodiacetic acid and the secondary ligand amino acid is more. Iminodiacetic acid bears two negative charges and hence the coordinating tendency of the secondary ligand L to combine with [M(IMDA)] decreases significantly. Therefore, the mixed ligand formation constant values are significantly lower than K_{ML}^M and slightly lower than $K_{ML_2}^M$. The $\log K_{ML}^M - \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ value is higher than unity in case of Zn(II) and lower in case of Cd(II). This is due to the smaller size of Zn(II) and bigger size of Cd(II), respectively. Besides the